

Pattern of Abnormalities in Liver Function Tests and Drug-Induced Liver Injury (DILI) Among Inpatients in a Tertiary Care HospitalAgnik Pal¹, Arijit Ghosh², Swastik Purkait³, Bodhisatwa Biswas⁴, Sukanta Sen⁵, Santanu Kumar Tripathi⁶¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Santiniketan Medical College and Hospital, Bolpur, West Bengal 731204²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Murshidabad Medical College & Hospital, Station Road, Berhampore, Murshidabad, West Bengal 742101³Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, JIS Institute of Medical Science & Research, 51 South Nayabaz, G.I.P Colony, Domjur, Howrah, West Bengal 711112⁴Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Banbishnupur, Purba Medinipur, Haldia, West Bengal 721645⁵Professor & Head, Department of Pharmacology, ICARE Institute of Medical Sciences and Research, Haldia, West Bengal 721645⁶Professor and Principal, Department of Pharmacology, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Kolkata, West Bengal 700137

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Abstract:**Background:** Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) accounts for almost every second acute liver failure and often leads to drug withdrawal, boxed warnings or drug non-approval. Dose-related and thus predictable DILI is a rarity, making a quantification of the hepatotoxic risk of drugs necessary.**Materials & Methods:** Consecutive 100 patients who were admitted in the medicine ward and with abnormal LFT results satisfying the inclusion & exclusion criteria after obtaining informed consent were enrolled for the study and evaluated using structured questionnaire and clinical examinations. Abnormal liver function test was defined as Total Bilirubin > 1mg/dl, ALT > 41 U/L, AST > 38 U/L, GGT > 58 U/L, ALP > 96 U/L.**Results:** In this study we found out that among 100 study participants, the most common diagnosis of abnormal LFT was Viral Hepatitis (41%). Drug induced Hepatitis (DILI) & Alcoholic hepatitis were also responsible for a significant proportion at 26% & 24% respectively. In this study it was revealed that Drug induced Liver Injury (DILI) most commonly caused by rifampicin at standard dosage used in treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis (23%) followed by antifungal drugs (19.2%), isoniazid & pyrazinamide (both 15.3%).**Conclusion:** In summary, our study identified a large number of drugs as possible causes of DILI. In all patients with newly developed jaundice or abnormal laboratory results of liver tests drug aetiology must be included as a differential diagnosis and a precise medication history has to be taken.**Keywords:** Liver Function Test, Drug-Induced Liver Injury (DILI).This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Identification of abnormal liver biochemical tests is one of the most common findings during health examinations (8.9%).^[1] Interpreting abnormal liver function tests (LFTs) and trying to diagnose any underlying liver disease is a common scenario in routine clinical practice. Abnormal LFTs may be asymptomatic and are often inadequately investigated - which may miss an early opportunity of identifying and treating chronic liver disease.^[2] The primary problem may be the liver, or the abnormal results can be secondary to other problems elsewhere in the body.^[3] Alternatively,

there may be nothing wrong with the liver at all. The evaluation of abnormal LFTs in a hospitalized patient tends to assume more urgency than that in the outpatient setting. The preliminary step is a determination as to whether the abnormal LFTs are associated with the initial reason for the patient's hospitalization, are secondary to a chronic underlying liver disease preceding the admission or developed in hospital. A careful history, either directly from the patient or family members, a review of patient's records, and/or discussion to the patient's physician may be critical in providing the

necessary information. LFT abnormalities fall into several patterns which help in differentiating the underlying liver disease, indicative of hepatocellular damage (high serum transaminase), cholestasis (high alkaline phosphatase) or poor synthetic function. Although a liver biopsy is the gold standard for assessing both aetiology and the degree of fibrosis, it is associated with some morbidity and should be undertaken only after assessing the risk benefit. The clinical setting, together with the specific pattern of LFT abnormality and appropriate additional tests, can narrow the differential diagnosis and provide a cost-effective approach to identifying those patients who need a liver biopsy.[3]

Drug-induced liver injury (DILI) is a leading health problem especially in a globally expanding commercialization of new drugs and the increasing exposure of patients to new compounds. This is expected to increase because of the number of drugs being consumed, prescription and non-prescription, as well as because of the current tendency towards pharmacologically active complementary and alternative medicines, dietary supplements, recreational substances and special diets.[4]

As a consequence, DILI ranks as the first cause of acute liver failure in USA accounting for 13% of all cases of acute liver failure and is the main reason for post-commercialization decisions by regulatory bodies and withdrawal of drugs from the market despite of a rigorous pre-clinical and clinical review process.[5] DILI is a relatively neglected disease because of the rarity of its diagnosis and the difficulty of attribution of causality. However, the real incidence of DILI remains unknown because of the difficulty in establishing diagnosis and the low reporting frequency to the pharmacovigilance authorities.[6] In India, study on the abnormalities in LFT test results as well as the presentations and identifications of DILI patients are scarce, that provides a strong rationale for the present study.

Materials & Methods

The study was a prospective observational, non-randomized study (Fig. 1). The data for the study was collected from the patients admitted to both male & female in-patient department (IPDs) under Department of Tropical Medicine. Data compilation and analysis were done in Department of Clinical & Experimental Pharmacology at School of Tropical Medicine, Kolkata. The study was conducted after getting approval on the study after the study design & study techniques were approved by the Clinical Research Ethics

Committee of the institution. A written, fully informed consent was taken from all the patients who were enrolled in this study. Study participants were selected in a nonrandomized convenience sampling method and the study was conducted for 6 months. The study was done and informed consent process was undertaken in accordance with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975 that was revised in 2013, latest ICMR Guidelines and the Indian GCP Guidelines. Consecutive 100 patients who were admitted in the medicine ward, and with abnormal LFT results satisfying the inclusion & exclusion criteria after obtaining informed consent were enrolled for the study and evaluated using structured questionnaire and clinical examinations. Abnormal liver function test was defined as Total Bilirubin > 1mg/dl [7], ALT > 41 U/L, AST > 38 U/L, GGT > 58 U/L, ALP > 96 U/L.[8] Pre-set inclusion-exclusion criteria were used to screen the study participants.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients admitted in IPD of Department of Tropical Medicine during the days of data collection for the study
- Patients having abnormal liver function test reports at the time of hospital admission. (both in house & outside reports were considered)
- Patients alert, conscious and able to undergo interview for the study
- Both male & female gender recruited (from both Male & Female wards)
- Willingness to participate

Exclusion Criteria

- OPD patients
- Critically ill patients – needing intensive medical attention (like stroke, myocardial infarction, acute poisoning, snake bite etc.)
- Patients who were in altered sensorium state
- Audio visually impaired patients

Study Techniques: The patients were subjected to detailed assessment including focused interview and history elicitation with a particular emphasis on medication history and relevant clinical examinations.

A focused evaluation of abnormal LFT results was done in correlation with patients' conditions and treatments. An appropriate case report form (CRF) was designed to gather data.

All the data were compiled, tabulated, and analysed using statistical software -latest versions of Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) by IBM & Ms Excel by Microsoft.

Figure 1: Study procedure

Results: In this study we found out that among 100 study participants, the most common diagnosis of abnormal LFT was Viral Hepatitis (41%). Drug induced Hepatitis (DILI) & Alcoholic hepatitis were also responsible for a significant proportion at 26% & 24% respectively. Results were represented with suitable tables & diagrams (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Pie chart showing distribution of different etiologies for abnormal LFTs among the study participants. (N=100)

In this study it was revealed that drug induced liver injury (DILI) most commonly caused by rifampicin at standard dosage used in treatment of pulmonary tuberculosis (23%). followed by antifungal drugs (19.2%), isoniazid & pyrazinamide (both 15.3%) [Table 1/ Fig. 2-3].

Table 1: Showing the frequency of drugs causing DILI

Suspected Drugs	Frequency of drugs responsible for DILI	Percentage (%)
Rifampicin	6	23%
Antifungals	5	19.2%
Isoniazid	4	15.3%
Pyrazinamide	4	15.3%
NSAIDs	3	11.5%
Nevirapine	2	8%
Efavirenz	1	3.8%
Cotrimoxazole	1	3.8%
Statins	1	3.8%

Figure 3: Pie Chart showing the distribution of suspected drugs responsible for DILI among the study participants who have DILI. (26 patients)

Discussion

In our study, the most common cause of finding abnormal LFT was viral hepatitis (41%) followed by drug induced liver injury & alcoholic liver disease (26% & 24% respectively). Viral hepatitis is common cause of elevation in LFTs. Viral hepatitis B, C, and D can cause chronic hepatitis, while hepatitis A and E cause acute viral hepatitis.[9] Different other viruses, like Epstein-Barr (EBV), Cytomegalovirus (CMV), HIV etc. can also cause hepatitis.[10] The hepatic manifestation of heavy alcohol consumption is referred to as alcoholic liver disease (ALD), which encompasses a wide spectrum of disorders including fatty liver, alcoholic steatohepatitis (ASH), alcoholic hepatitis (AH), cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma.[11][12][13]

DILI, on the other hand, may result from direct toxicity of the administered drug or their metabolites, or injury may occur from immune-mediated mechanisms.[14] DILI is difficult to diagnose. Diagnosis is mainly based on circumstantial evidence because of low incidence & limited knowledge of the biochemical mechanism(s) or pathways responsible for this. Hence it is termed 'idiosyncratic' adverse event. Clinically, DILI usually culminates between 5 and 90 days after drug ingestion and presents with wide spectrum of symptoms and signs - ranging from asymptomatic rise of hepatic enzymes (SGPT & SGOT), acute or chronic hepatitis to acute liver failure (ALF) or fulminant hepatic failure.[15] As there is no gold standard for diagnosis, it is

necessary to explore multiple facets like medical history, presentation, laboratory results, and progression. However, the pattern of drug-related liver injury is classified according to laboratory data [16] since the liver biopsy specimen is frequently not available, from a practical standpoint.

The Councils for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) [16][17] categories DILI into three types: Hepatocellular, Cholestatic, and Mixed. 'Hepatocellular type is defined by alanine aminotransferase (ALT) > 2 ULN (upper limits of normal) or $R \geq 5$, where R is the ratio of serum activity of ALT/serum activity of alkaline phosphatase (ALP), both of which are expressed as multiples of the ULN. Liver injury is likely to be more severe in hepatocellular type than in cholestatic /mixed type. Patients with elevated bilirubin levels in hepatocellular liver injury are more prone to develop serious liver injury with fatalities, and are found at a rate of 0.7 to 1.3/100 000 individuals exposed to a given drug. [18]

Susceptibility to DILI is assumed to be associated with some patient related factors such as age and sex, though there is no exclusive evidence to define increased risk in any given patient subpopulation. A complex interaction between the chemical properties of the drug and environmental factors (e.g., the use of concomitant drugs or alcohol), age, sex, underlying diseases (e.g., HIV or diabetes), and genetic factors usually determine the risk of developing hepatotoxicity.[19] The major factors for diagnosis of DILI include the time to onset,

clinical features, the time and course of recovery, specific risk factors, the exclusion of other diagnoses, and previous reports on the hepatotoxicity of the culprit medication. The diagnosis can be further confirmed by response to suspension of suspected drug, rechallenge and, in some cases, if possible, liver biopsy.[20]

The most reliable risk factors are concomitant drug use and diseases among the speculated factors. DILI cases appear to be increasing among patients with HIV, hepatitis B virus, and hepatitis C virus infection, which suggests a role for cytokine imbalance in these patients as well as genetic factors that control the pharmacokinetics of the drug such as metabolism, detoxification, and transport, and those that influence cell injury and repair.[21] Additionally, genetic polymorphisms with functional effects occur with many of the genes that encode drug-metabolizing enzymes and drug transporters.[22] Apart from total bilirubin and the hepatocellular type of injury, other variables such older age, female gender, and AST levels were independently associated with a poor outcome.[23]

In our study, we have found most cases of DILI with suspected drug as rifampicin, followed by antifungals, then isoniazid and pyrazinamide. Some cases were suspected due to NSAIDs, nevirapine, efavirenz, cotrimoxazole and statin. In this current study, anti-tubercular drugs were identified as most common culprit agents implicated in DILI. This high incidence is in accordance with earlier studies by Kshirsagar et al and Jaiprakash, et al.[24][25] Antifungal drugs are also implicated commonly in different studies, most commonly reported with voriconazole (32.45%), fluconazole (19.37%), and itraconazole (14.51%) from a recent FDA Adverse Event Reporting System Database study [26], which is in line with our study finding of approximately 20% of total DILIs were caused by antifungals.

NSAIDs are also instrumental in causing DILI, with studies showed diclofenac, celecoxib, ibuprofen, etodolac and meloxicam might be most commonly responsible.[27] We have also found some DILI cases caused by NSAIDs. All antiretroviral drugs can cause DILI.[28] Non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTI) such as nevirapine have been shown to induce DILI in 12%-17% of the patients, which is three times more than that caused by EFV in various studies.[29][30]

These corroborates with our study. Besides, antibiotics are also considered as one of the commonest causes of DILI, with frequency of serious antibiotic-induced hepatotoxicity is low compared with the amounts prescribed each year-in <5 per 100000 population and remains a main

reason for antibiotic withdrawal after product launch. [31][32][33] Within antibiotics, cotrimoxazole is one of the most common antibiotic implicated in different studies, to the tune of 13%–23% of drug-induced hepatotoxicity cases [34][35] and similarly also found out to be one of the causative agent for DILI in our study. Lastly, statin induced liver injury presenting in either hepatocellular or cholestatic patterns and in differing LFT value changes are often found [36], and also took position as one of implicating agent in our study.

Conclusion

The incidence of DILI is continually increasing, reflecting the increasing number of new drugs and other causative agents that have been introduced into clinical use over the past several decades. Most cases with deranged liver function tests were diagnosed as virus hepatitis. It is in line with the studies that reflected that viral hepatitis is a major healthcare burden in India with comparable threat as “big three” communicable diseases like HIV/AIDS, malaria and tuberculosis.¹⁵ Apart from this, drug groups like antitubercular, antifungal, antiretrovirals, antibiotics, statins etc. often landing up with grave changes in LFT and hepatic toxicity. The present study was conducted to assess the nature and pattern of abnormal LFTs as well as suspected drug induced liver injury among in-patients. Large real-world outcomes studies are needed to find out discrete patterns of these serious conditions in South Asian population.

Ethical Approval: This study was approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Calcutta School of Tropical Medicine- CREC-STM /45 dated 26.09.2013.

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